

Empowerment through Law : An analysis of Women's Right and Legal Provisions in India

Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar

Assistant prof. in Department of Law

Shivaji University Kolhapur

Abstract

Women's rights form the point of view of a just and equitable society and in India, the legal framework has played a crucial role in shaping the path toward gender justice. This research paper explores the evolution scope and impact of legal provisions that aims to empower women in India. Drawing upon constitutional guarantees, statutory protections and judicial pronouncements, the study critically examines how laws address issues such as discrimination violence, workplace inequality and access to resources. It highlights key legislations including the evolution of new laws that enacted to protect the rights of women. The paper also evaluates the effectiveness of these provisions in bridging the gap between legal rights and lived realities while identifying persistent challenges such as patriarchal norms, implementation gaps and lack of awareness. By analyzing the interplay between law society and women empowerment the research highlight the importance of strengthening legal mechanisms and promoting gender sensitive approaches to ensure substantive equality ultimately the study argues that law is not just a protective shield but also transformative instrument for advancing women's right and achieving empowerment in India.

Keywords- NCW, DPSP,

Introduction

"In recent years women empowerment faces lot of challenges. Women empowerment is one of the most important issue in today's society. Empowerment means giving women ability to make their own choices, live with dignity and have equal opportunities in all fields of society. In India the struggle for women's rights has long history and many laws have been made to protect and promote their rights".

"The Indian Constitution of India provides equally and justice to all citizens and several legal provisions have been introduced to safeguard women against discrimination, violence and injustice. However even with these laws women still face many challenges in achieving true equality. Social practices cultural traditions and lack of awareness often prevent women from enjoying their legal rights fully".

"Therefore it is important to study how laws in India work to empower women and what more can be done to make them effective. In women empowerment it is very important to analyze the legal provision for women's right in in India their role in empowering women and mitigate the gap. Women empowerment also highlight how legal measures can be used more effectively to ensure gender justice and create a society where women can live without freedom, respect and equality".

Hurdles in women empowerment

"Women empowerment in India faces several hurdles despite many legal and constitutional provisions. The 1st and biggest is social and cultural barriers. Deeply rooted traditions and patriarchal attitudes often restrict women's freedom. Practices like early marriage,

dowry and preference for sons over daughters reduce opportunities for women to grow equally. Another major hurdle is lack of education and awareness”.

“Many Women especially in rural areas are not aware of their legal rights. Without proper education they can't fight against injustice or make independent decisions about their lives. Economic dependency is also a serious problem. Women often do not have equal access to jobs property or financial resources”.

“This make them dependent on male members of their family and limits their ability to live freely. Violence and safety issues create fear and insecurity. Crimes like domestic violence, sexual harassment and trafficking discourage women from participating fully in society. Even though there are strict laws, lack of effective implementation makes the problem worse”.

Women empowerment and Constitutional provisions

“The Indian legal system provides many provisions for women's right and empowerment. The constitution of India guarantees equality before law (Article 14), prohibits discrimination on the basis of sex (Article 15) and allows the state to make special provisions for women (article 15(3)). It also ensures the duty to renounce practices against the dignity of women (Article 51A) Judiciary has also played a big role in expanding women's rights. In many cases the Supreme Court and high courts have progressive judgments that protect women's dignity and promote gender justice. in Directive principles of state policy Article 39(a),(d), and € ensuring adequate means of livelihood, equal pay for equal work and protection of women from exploitation. Article 42 explains provision for just and humane conditions of work and maternity relief. And Article 51 A€ explains fundamental duty to renounce practices derogatory to dignity of women”.

Personal laws and women's rights.

“Personal laws in India governs marriage, maintenance, inheritance and property rights they differ according to realign but over the time, reforms have aimed to ensure importance in equality and empowerment of women. India has developed a strong legal framework to empower women by ensuring equality, protecting from violence, securing workplace rights and promoting political participation. Key legislations such as Hindu Succession Act work to remove social barriers in women empowerment. Personal laws in India reflect both progressive reforms and traditional limitations. These reforms in divorce and maintenance have significantly improved women's property and marital rights. True empowerment lies not only in passing progressive laws but also in ensuring awareness, enforcement and gender justice across communities”.

Hindu Succession Act 1956(Amendment in 2005)

“Originally this act gave sons equal right in ancestral property but daughters were excluded. But in 2005 made amendment and included daughters were recognized as coparceners (joint heirs) in Hindu undivided Family (HUF) equal to sons. A daughters has the same rights and liabilities as a son in ancestral property. Women can now demand partition of ancestral property and have full ownership of inherited property. This act amendment made impact and strengthen economic empowerment of Hindu women by granting them equal inheritance rights”.

Hindu Marriage Act 1955

“This law regulates marriage, divorce and related rights. Originally progressive it has been further amended to protect women's rights. In 1976 this act amended for equal grounds for divorce. Earlier husband and wife had unequal grounds for divorce. Amendments made grounds

uniform such as cruelty, desertion (2 years), mental disorder, venereal disease, renunciation etc. right to divorce on special grounds for women gave stronger remedies. Women have rights in children's custody matters ensuring children's welfare prioritized. In the restitution of conjugal rights courts now interpret it cautiously to protect women from being forced back into abusive marriages. These provisions empowered women to end abusive or unequal marriages, provided financial security and recognized their dignity and independence”.

Hindu Adoption and maintenance Act 1956

“This act amendment gives women the right to adopt a child in her own name previously only men could. This act mandates that a husband must provide maintenance to his wife during the marriage and even after separation if she can't maintain herself. It includes maintenance rights for widow's unmarried daughters and dependents”.

Maternity Benefit Act 1961(amended in 2017)

“In this act provides 26 weeks of paid maternity leave for women working in establishments with 10 or more employees earlier 12 week leave given. This act ensures economic security along with paid leave prevents income loss during maternity, strengthening financial independence.it helps to maintain balance between career and family, encouraging women to continue in the workplace. This act protects health and dignity and ensures women can take care of themselves and their newborn without fear of losing their job”.

Equal Remuneration Act 1976 (now under Code on wages 2019)

“This act ensures economic empowerment of women and not undervalued or exploited in terms of wages. Employers are legally bound to pay women and men the same wages for the same work. Equal pay motivates women to join and stay in workforce. It break gender stereotypes and legally challenges the notion that women's work is less valuable than men. Equal pay laws have been crucial in reducing gender wage gaps and pushing towards workplace justice directly impacting women's independence and empowerment”.

POSH Act 2013 and women's Right.

“The Sexual Harassment of women at workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act 2013 was enacted after the Vishaka v State of Rajasthan 1997. It provides a strong legal framework to protect women against sexual harassment at workplace. According to this act it is mandatory to establish Internal Complaints Committee for every workplace with 10 or more employees. This act provides a safe workplace, organize gender sensitization programs and assist women in filing complaints. This act ensures women can work without fear harassment creating an environment of dignity and respect. This act gave women statutory protection backed by strict procedures”.

National Commission for women Act 1990

“The NCW Act 1990 established as a statutory body to protect and promote women's right in India. Its main objective is to review constitutional and legal safeguards for women. It recommend remedial legislative measures. Under NCW act there is establishment of a statutory body as national and state commission for women. NCW has played a pivotal role in reviewing existing legal provisions, recommending amendments to discriminatory laws and suggesting new legislative measures to strengthen women's rights. Its proactive interventions in cases of atrocities, trafficking workplace harassment, dowry related violence and other rights violations have ensured that women's issues are not ignored but are addressed with seriousness. Beyond redressal the NCW has also contributed to awareness-building, research and policy formulation thereby strengthening the legal and social fabric of women's empowerment”.

Conclusion

“Women empowerment through law is a continuous process. Law provides a strong foundation for equality but real change will happen only when society changes its mindsets

women are educated and aware of their rights and laws are implementing strictly. By combining legal provisions with social awareness India can move closer to build society where women enjoy equal status, dignity and opportunities. Women empowerment is an important step towards achieving equality and justice in society. The Indian Constitution and various legal provisions have created a strong framework to protect women's rights, ensure their safety and equal opportunities. However only legal provisions alone can't bring complete Women empowerment. Social barriers, lack of awareness and weak implementation of laws continue to limit women from enjoying their rights fully. True Women empowerment will possible only when legal measures are supported by education, economic independence and a change in social attitudes”.

Findings

1. “Constitutional safeguards such as equality before law, prohibition of discrimination and right to dignity provide a strong foundation for women's empowerment.
2. Statutory provisions like Hindu Succession Act (amended), Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, Maternity Benefit Act, and workplace harassment laws have significantly improved women's legal status.
3. Despite progressive laws, implementation gaps and lack of awareness among women reduce their effectiveness.
4. Sociocultural barriers such as patriarchy, stereotypes and lack of education continue to hinder women from fully exercising their rights.
5. Legal provisions are more effective in urban areas compared to rural settings due to difference in literacy, accessibility and enforcement mechanisms”.

Suggestions

1. “Strengthen the legal implementation and ensure strict enforcement of existing women centric laws through effective monitoring and accountability mechanisms.
2. Increase legal awareness and conduct legal literacy campaigns, especially in rural and marginalized communities so women know their rights and remedies.
3. In society need to promote gender sensitization and train police officers, judges and government officials to handle women's issues with empathy and sensitivity.
4. Encourage political participation to provide greater representation of women in decision making bodies through reservation and leadership training”.

Bibliography

1. M.P. Jain, 'Indian Constitutional Law', vol-I (5th Ed., 2003, Wadhwa Nagpur).
2. Durga Das Basu, 'Commentary on the Constitution of India', vol-II (8th Ed., 2008, Lexis Nexis, Butterworth Wadhwa).
3. paliwala, Law and crisis. 5. Ahuja, Sangeeta, People, Law and Justice.A Case Book on PIL, Vol.I, Orient Longman Ltd., New Delhi, 1997.
4. Austin, Granville, The Indian Constitution – Cornerstone of a Nation, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 1996.
5. Mishra, Shweta , *Women and 73 rd Constitutional Amendment Act: A Critical Appraisal* , Social Action, Vol.44, 16-30, (1997)
6. **The Politics of Women's Rights in India.**, Flavia Agnes, Oxford University Press, 1999,
7. **Off the Beaten Track: Rethinking Gender Justice for Indian Women** by Madhu Kishwar OUP, New Delhi: 1999
8. **Girl Child in Indian Society** Mita Bhadra (ed.) Rawat Publications New Delhi: 1999